

CONSENT FORM FOR PUBLICATION

1. Introduction

You are invited to participate in a research study on the influence of emotions in the field of trading. The goal of this study is to deepen the understanding of individual investors' decision-making. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary.

2. Study Description

If you agree to participate, you will be involved in an online experiment involving trading simulations. The information you provide, such as your investment choices, emotional reactions, and decisions, will be collected and analyzed as part of this study.

3. Duration and Nature of Participation

The duration of your participation will be three days, and it will take place in person (at the University of Mons on an online platform).

4. Risks and Benefits

No major physical risks are associated with your participation in this study. Your results may contribute to a better understanding of individual investor behavior and will be used in academic publications.

5. Confidentiality

The data collected during the study will be handled confidentially and used solely for the purposes of this research. No information that could identify you will be published.

6. Consent

By signing this form, you confirm that you have read and understood the information above and that you freely consent to participate in this study. You also agree that the data you provide may be used for research purposes under the conditions mentioned above.

You may ask any questions you wish before signing, and this consent can be withdrawn at any time, without consequence.

7. Signature

Participant's Name : _____

Participant's Signature : _____

Date : _____